

Work Engagement of Lecturer in Higher Education: Studies at State Universities in Indonesia

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Keywords

Abstract

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Lecturers as educators who deal with students in conveying the learning process, are expected to be motivated in work and committed, enthusiastic, and passionate in doing their work. Lecturer performance is the basis for achieving organizational performance. To provide maximum performance, every lecturer needs to have good work involvement. This study aims to determine the work involvement of lecturers in universities in Indonesia. This study uses a literature review obtained from secondary data in the form of articles from previous research. The results of previous studies show that there are several things that affect the work involvement of lecturers in universities in Indonesia, namely job characteristics, awards, and recognition.

1. Introduction

Employee engagement has become a major phenomenon in both the academic and business domains over the past two decades, companies suggest that engaged employees are not only more productive (Hakanen and Koivumäki, 2014; Harter et al., 2013) but also experience better well-being in the workplace. inside and outside the workplace (Freeney and Fellenz, 2013; Hakanen and Peeters, 2015). The potential for reciprocal rewards for both parties in the employment relationship has led management research to devote a great deal of attention to how an engaged workforce can be developed and maintained. However, most of this research was conducted in the private sector such

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as the research conducted by Consiglio et al., (2016); Farndale et al., (2014) and Shantz et al., (2016) and academics have highlighted that the literature has paid relatively less attention to understanding the concept of employee engagement in public sector organizations (Jeve et al., 2015; Jones and Sambrook, 2016; Vigoda-Gadot et al., 2012). There is a difference between work involvement in the private sector and the public sector. Where in the public sector is characterized by the existence of a hierarchy, a centralized organizational structure, limited flexibility and little opportunity to get an award from the aspect of work that can increase high work involvement.

Lecturers at universities expand their role as education in order to facilitate the development of graduates who are competent and balanced intellectually, emotionally, physically and spiritually. Diversification of job responsibilities currently requires lecturers to manage multiple roles which include teachers, researchers, counselors and administrators compared to before where lecturers were more focused on teaching (Safiah et al., 2012).

Lecturers as talented people, who deal with students in conveying the learning process, are expected to be motivated to work and committed, enthusiastic, and passionate in doing their work. Lecturer performance is the basis for achieving organizational performance. Every lecturer as a lecturer must enrich performance with *Tridharma*. According to Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, it is stated that universities are obliged to provide three obligations called *Tridharma*, namely lectures, research, and community service. Lecturer workload is the main task of professional educators and scientists to transform, develop, and disseminate science, technology, and art through education, research, and community service (dikti.go.id, 2010). Therefore, lecturers as employees need several conditions that will lead to loyalty and survival at the University. Lecturer perceptions are important to define because perception is a process of giving meaning to the environment by individuals (Gibson et al, 2006). The condition of lecturer attachment as an employee is a feeling that makes employees feel more enthusiastic about work that tries to show their best performance, is loyal and stays in the organization. This is in line with the statement of Robins and Judge (2013) that employee engagement is an employee's positive attitude towards the values and goals of the organization. By involving workers, the organization will try to have an understanding and awareness of how to achieve its goals in the long term.

2. Materials and Methods

Work Engagement Concept

Employee engagement is one such construct. The dual understanding of the colloquial term 'engaged' has led to a variety of different meanings being attached to the concept in both academia and practice. The ambiguous nature of this concept is further driven by the different variations of terms used in the literature such as 'employee engagement', 'work engagement', 'work engagement', 'personal engagement' and 'organizational engagement' (Truss et al, 2014). Bakker and Leiter (2010) argue that job involvement describes the ability of employees to use employee capacities to solve problems, connect with people, and develop innovative services. Companies also need employees who are bound by their work because employees who have a high level of work engagement will show the best performance at work (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). Employee engagement has a positive impact on the organization. Indicators of job involvement include positive work, satisfaction, and well-being. Schaufeli & Bakker (2010) also state that positive feelings and work engagement are the result of a person's meaning of his work. Schaufeli & Bakker (2010) defines job involvement as psychological involvement that involves two important components, namely attention and absorption. Attention

refers to the cognitive behavior and the amount of time an employee spends in carrying out his or her role, while absorption refers to the meaning of the role and refers to the intensity of an employee towards his or her role in the organization. The indicators of work involvement are commitment, enthusiasm, absorption, focused effort, and energy.

The most widely adopted conceptualization of engagement in academia is that proposed by Schaufeli et al. (2002:74) who use the term 'job engagement' and define it as 'a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind characterized by passion, dedication and absorption'. Vigor relates to employees who are very energetic so they are willing to invest a high level of effort in their work (Schaufeli, 2014). Dedication refers to an employee who is highly involved in their work and feels enthusiastic, inspired and proud of what they do (Schaufeli, 2014). Absorption is translated into feelings of pleasure and concentration of employees at work so that time passes by (Schaufeli, 2014)

Job Engagement Theory

Job engagement refers to a persistent and pervasive cognitive-affective state that focuses not only on specific objects, events, individuals, or behaviors, but also on general conditions at work. Kahn (1990) defines work engagement as an employee's effort to carry out job duties and responsibilities using self-expression, cognitive and emotional. Ghorbannejad and Esakhani (2016) suggest that employee engagement and work engagement have the same characteristics and shaping aspects. Work engagement is a condition where a person has a positive mind, he is able to express himself physically, cognitively and affectively in doing his job (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Job involvement is a work-related condition that is positive, satisfying, motivational, affective well-being (Leiter & Bakker, 2010). between individuals as a function of working conditions, personal characteristics, and behavioral strategies. Knowledge of work engagement from an individual perspective is considered insufficient to explain work engagement in work and organizational life. Bakker and Demerouti (2018) describe work engagement as a positive, satisfying, and related mental state of mind about work that is characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption. In the study of Bakker, Demerouti, and Sanz-vergel (2014), work engagement is characterized by high energy and strong identification with work. Work engagement is characterized by awareness of the meaning of work where people feel they have high energy, enthusiasm, mental endurance at work,

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Deligero & Laguador (2014) define employee engagement as the level of employees' psychological investment in their organization. Job engagement drives employees to higher levels of productivity in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in the workplace (Deligero & Laguador, 2014). Evidently, the employees involved have a strong will and desire to continuously improve their practice. The commitment, creativity, and other characteristics of highly effective employees cannot be underlined. Their willingness to work beyond what is expected of them and keep up with developments in their field of work makes them appreciated and recognized by their immediate superiors (Robinson et al., 2004). Of course, Employee work engagement greatly contributes to the achievement of organizational results that are in line with the organization's vision and mission (Steger et al. 2013). Employees who are organizationally engaged experience a positive and energetic relationship with the organization they work for and derive fulfillment from the organization's mission and values (Saks and Gruman, 2014). As such, they are enthusiastic and dedicated to helping the organization achieve its goals (Farndale et al., 2014). They feel happy to be members of the organization and try to be involved in what is happening in the organization (Saks, 2006). As such,

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Lecturer Work Involvement in Higher Education

Research has shown that organizations with highly engaged employees are healthier, happier, and more productive and provide better services to citizens. As a result, improving the work environment by developing stronger and more effective organizational improvement strategies has an impact on our employees and the citizens we serve (Hawkins, 2014). Some existing literature reports that institutions that allocate high teaching and workloads lead to higher stress and emotional burden among lecturers (Rohana et al., 2009; Kumar & Muniandy, 2012). Lecture capacity and demands lead to higher stress levels, decreased teaching effectiveness and lower satisfaction for their work among lecturers in higher education institutions (Anas et al., 2014; Wan Ibrahim & Syarif Muhidin, 2015). Lecturers' dissatisfaction with their work is caused by heavy workloads, poor benefits and low salary levels (Chimanikar et al., 2007). In addition, lecturers are more likely to exhibit negative behaviors such as decreased productivity, poor teaching quality, higher intention to leave the educational institution (Mxenge, Dywili & Bazana, 2014; Rathakrishnan, Ng & Tee, 2016) and reduced levels of work engagement and commitment. against institutions (Muhamad Zaid et al., 2014). According to Zainuddin, Junaidah and Nazmi (2010), lecturers without commitment will leave the teaching profession or remain and avoid their routine responsibilities.

Research Method

The method used in this study is a literature review that uses sources from reference books, as well as leading international journals in the EBSCO database, Scopus (Schimago Journal Ranking), Science Direct, Proquest, Google Scholar, and Microsoft. Topics on the motivation of educators in higher education

3. Results and Discussions

According to Dewi (2020) lecturers are the spearhead of higher education because lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through education and community service. The duties of educators are described in Article 39 paragraph (1) which contains notes on planning and implementing: the learning process, assessing learning outcomes, conducting guidance and, conducting research and community service (Nuraeni, 2010).

The quality is determined from the implementation of the learning, research and service processes. In addition, to support the achievement of institutional accreditation, there is an involvement of lecturers in the process of preparing and realizing the accreditation of higher education institutions. According to research conducted by Dewiana et al (2018), it shows that the factors that influence the work involvement of lecturers in Indonesia include job characteristics, rewards, and recognition, perceptions of organizational support and supervisors. Then there are other things that affect the work involvement of university lecturers in Indonesia, namely empowerment and psychological contracts. A high level of psychological contract from employees,

will improve employee performance. This is because employees feel proud to be able to work in a company that has fulfilled their expectations and desires (Alexandri, 2018). Furthermore, another study conducted by Dewi et al (2020) who conducted research at a private university in Yogyakarta showed that a high or low level of quality of work life will affect the work involvement of lecturers.

Lecturers who have a positive perception of the quality of work will feel in accordance with their work and institution so that lecturers will work as optimally as possible to improve their competence so that they can contribute maximally to the progress of the institution. Research conducted by Nagalingan et al (2019), the findings through this study indicate the importance of emotional intelligence in encouraging work engagement and organizational commitment among lecturers. This finding emphasizes the importance of higher education institutions to place a strong emphasis on the growth of emotional intelligence abilities among lecturers because this approach will encourage positive work behaviors such as engagement and subsequently greater commitment to the institution. Research conducted by Nagalingan et al (2019), the findings through this study indicate the importance of emotional intelligence in encouraging work engagement and organizational commitment among lecturers.

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Based on the results of previous studies, there are several things that affect the work involvement of lecturers at universities in Indonesia, namely job characteristics, rewards, and recognition, perceptions of organizational and supervisor support, the level of quality of work life and emotional intelligence.

Employee engagement is a complex issue in HRM. If an organization wants to have a competitive advantage, it needs employees with good performance and restraint. The reason is that employee engagement will make employees feel happy and enthusiastic to work with good performance (Handoko, 2010). Employee engagement can be divided into three aspects: physical/personal, emotional and cognitive aspects. The physical aspect is the level of personal involvement with the organization. The emotional aspect can be realized by conditions where employees are willing to cooperate or empathize with superiors and co-workers. The cognitive aspect is awareness of the role played by the organization. Characteristics of employee engagement with regard to the organization In general,

Employees who are involved will increase their commitment to company goals, complete tasks to the best of their ability, behave well at work, and will ensure that tasks have been carried out properly according to objectives and are ready for improvement or evaluation if needed. (Marciano, 2010). According to an Osney Media Ltd survey, employee engagement is a top priority experienced by approximately 82% of respondents. Employee engagement is basically in accordance with a person's commitment and satisfaction with his work, or it can be said that employee engagement is a form of job satisfaction in a modern context (Schmidtdkk., 1993). Therefore, employee engagement will have an impact on increasing employee performance which is one of the successes of a company (Siddhanta & Roy, 2010).

4. Conclusion

Lecturers at universities are required to have good work involvement to encourage performance in fulfilling the *Tridharma*. Several things that affect the work involvement of lecturers at universities in Indonesia are job characteristics, rewards, and recognition, perceptions of organizational support and supervisors, the level of quality of work life and emotional intelligence. Every higher education institution is important to pay attention to this because it will have an impact on improving employee performance which is one of the successes of a company. This study only examines job involvement in universities in Indonesia. For further research, it is possible to develop research in several countries in order to compare work involvement in several countries.

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